

Traffic Robbery and Victimization in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper discusses strategies used by traffic robbers to dispossess unsuspecting motorists during traffic congestion in Lagos state, Nigeria. Traffic robbery has been a serious problem in the Lagos metropolis for many years. Recently, there has been an increased number of attacks on motorists and commuters who are stuck in traffic jams. Yet, studies on urban crimes in Lagos are yet to analyse the experiences of victims of traffic robbery. The nexus between time and space, which has significantly influenced the occurrence of robbery in Lagos traffic, has also been under-discussed. Routine activity theory is utilised to account for the experiences of victims of traffic robbery. The methodology of media monitoring and content analysis is utilised by analysing 167 traffic robbery cases reported in five various newspapers, namely: Vanguard, Tribune, Punch, The Guardian, and The Sun in Lagos State from 2015 to 2023. Newspaper key search word, “traffic robbery,” was used to gather data from the selected newspapers. The responses of victims, as derived from their experiences, were used qualitatively to analyse the data. The findings show that victims’ experiences were horrific, fear-driven, and pose mental health issues. It also reveals that timing is a crucial factor in understanding incidences of traffic robberies, as most violent crimes in Lagos traffic occurred between 9 p.m. and 11p.m. Traffic robbers use guns, knives, bottles, and charms as instruments to instigate fear in drivers and commuters, and dispossess them of their valuables. The conclusion of the paper is that more security presence is needed to curb traffic robbery in areas in Lagos prone to the crime.

Keywords: Crime Prevention, Robbery Hotspots, Routine Activity Theory, Traffic Robbery, Victimization.

Suggested Citation: I. G. Peter & F. O. Ajiola (2025), ‘Traffic Robbery and Victimization in Lagos State, Nigeria,’ *TzJMS*. Vol. 1. No. 1. pp. 64-83.

Peer Reviewed

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper investigates the dynamics of traffic robbery in Lagos State. Traffic robbery is a significant urban problem globally. However, the perennial traffic situation in Lagos State, Nigeria, has transformed urban highways to centres of armed robbery. There are rampant criminal activities targeted usually at individuals operating or occupying areas in which there are stationary or slow-moving vehicles, especially in densely populated parts of Lagos. (Haruna and Ochigbo, 2021). Metropolitan cities like Lagos are characterised by high traffic and reckless driving, which give robbers who operate during traffic situations the leeway to carry out their nefarious activities. As part of their strategies, the robbers closely monitor traffic situations and leverage opportunity to perpetuate their criminal acts. Robbery during traffic situation is an organised crime which threatens security of lives and properties in most urban areas, especially contemporary Lagos. A prominent example of traffic robbers in contemporary Lagos State is the “Omo no Salary boys,” which comprised “Street thugs.” This category of traffic robbers generates income for their livelihood mainly by exploiting vulnerable commuters by forcefully dispossessing them of their belongings in traffic scenes.

Robbery has to do with the forceful dispossession of one’s property or belongings through the use of threat or force. Incidents of robbery have increased, due to either the absence or ineffectiveness of security agents like the police. This absence of security agents has made it easy for criminals to freely carry out various operations in the city, both at night and during the day (Nnadozie *et al.*, 2023). Criminals focus more on victims, creating intense fear on commuters. Lagos traffic robbery involves the use of force or threat to dispossess motorists and commuters of their valuables. Crimes, like traffic robbery, have serious negative consequences on the economy. Businesses located in areas in which the robberies are perpetrated are affected, due mainly to the fear that is part of the aftermath of the crime. So, businesses around where traffic robbery occurs suffer various forms of victimization, as shops are closed early for business, because of fear of being robbed.

Traffic robberies are specific to time and space. Most individuals involved in traffic robberies are usually familiar with and stay close to the locations where the crimes are perpetrated, especially where there are weak forms of social control and organisation (Amram *et. al* 2024). What is observed in various cases of this kind of robbery is that robbers operate for a long period in a given place, with little or no presence of law enforcement agents. Drivers and commuters travelling in either motionless or slow-moving vehicles during traffic situations are mostly potential victims. This has negative consequences on victims, usually left with psychological damages as part of the aftermath of the incident. Traffic robbery can have various effects on victims, including on their physical health, employment and higher education prospects, finances and emotional wellbeing (Dinisman and Moroz 2017). One way the effect of traffic robbery can be

understood is creating support for victims in order to guarantee a better society. In the same way, an understanding of the coping mechanism can enhance understanding of the experiences faced by victims of traffic robbery. Victims of the crime experience shock and loss of trust in the society, as they believe that the incident could have been avoided (Dinisman and Moroz 2017). Victims also experience permanent trauma, as they reflect on the horrific experience, wishing it had never happened.

This study is, therefore, important. While most scholars focus on armed robbery incidents, they usually neglect the effect of traffic robbery on both armed robbery victims and the society. Most discussions focus less on experiences, suffering, violence, humiliation, and loss suffered by victims of traffic robbery. The extent of victims' losses determines the seriousness of crime (Ayodele and Aderinto, 2014). Sometimes, when victims lose money or any material thing as a result of an incident, it affects them directly, because of the harm the incident has caused them. The seriousness, in this context, is determined by the pain that has been inflicted on the victim. Law enforcement agency and the media often privilege certain crimes with greater losses and severity, because such crimes receive more empathy and attention. However, the experiences suffered by victims of traffic robbery are under-researched, because they are under-reported.

It would appear that traffic robberies cannot be avoided, given the dynamic and frequently chaotic nature of metropolitan surroundings. The disorderliness in cities can pose a challenge to citizens in regard to adhering to social standards, given opportunities for criminal elements to operate. The social, economic and psychological consequences of victims of traffic robbery are significant (Ayodele & Aderinto, 2014). This study, therefore, examines the consequences of traffic robbery on victims in some traffic-prone areas in Lagos.

There are four sub-sections in this paper. The first sub-section responds to whether or not time significantly influence traffic robbery. The second presents secondary data, such as newspapers, articles, and editorials, and examines victims' experiences of traffic robbery in Lagos state. The third sub-section engages the relevant theoretical approach that can aid understanding of the experience of victim in traffic robbery situation. However, the last outline concludes the discussion and makes recommendation.

2. TRAFFIC ROBBERS AND VICTIMS IN LAGOS STATE

Traffic robbery is a social problem that affects motorists and commuters plying the major traffic-congested roads in Lagos state. They take advantage of opportunities. Robbers take advantage of traffic situations and carry out operations using various tools. Due to the large number of cars in Lagos, motorists struggle to move vehicles in order to beat traffic. This has created traffic congestion and opportunity to traffic robbers. Since it is an organised crime, traffic robbers usually create artificial traffic by using different methods,

including blocking roads and using hawkers to execute their plans. Discussions are yet to be initiated on reports by various newspapers on traffic robbery incidents. However, there have been studies on the physical and material loss experienced by victims of traffic robbery (Tade and Olaitan, 2023).

There is need to understand the experiences faced by victims of traffic robbery. Some workers leave their workplace or business early in order not to experience traffic robbery. This has affected their level of productivity. Many individuals who have been victims of traffic robbery were either coming from their place of assignment or returning home. Traffic robbers are always on the alert to take advantage of any situation to attack their victims. Victims of traffic robbery have testified to how terrifying traffic robbery incident can be. One of the victims of traffic robbery testified thus:

I was coming back from work at Lekki, so I drove down the Third Mainland Bridge towards Ido, close to Ijora Olopa where the incident happened. There was light traffic. Those guys were robbing two cars ahead of me already. I couldn't reverse because there was traffic. I immediately wound up the glass to at least protect myself. But as soon as they finished with those two cars, I just heard sounds from the two sides of my car, they broke the side windscreen and began demanding my phone and other things. They entered and removed money from my safe. They had cutlasses and knives. One of them removed everything in my safe, and made away with my power bank, an iPhone 6 and a laptop (Oyewo, Punch, Sunday, August 24, 2023).

The victim revealed that he was on his way from work, when he was attacked by criminals in a traffic. The criminals that perpetrated this act were ready to rob many victims in order to keep up with their network of criminals. Traffic robbers took advantage of traffic situation to perpetrate their criminal act. Any location can be used by criminals to carry out their crime. But places which experience congestion or slow movement of cars are particularly flashpoints. The victim would have experienced the fate of others, if he had not shattered the wind screen of the car.

Another strategy used by traffic robbers is shattering of car glasses in order to gain access to valuable properties of victims in vehicles. A victim recounted:

I was descending Oshodi pedestrian bridge with my earphone on. Suddenly, Ahmed Kazeem brushed his

shoulder against mine. I noticed the music I was listening to stopped. I tried feeling my pocket to be sure, but my phone was no longer there. One of the passers-by who saw him told me Kazeem had stolen my phone, by then he had run away to the middle of the expressway, looking at me. Unfortunately for him, as we made to chase him, he was prevented from running further only for him to face our direction and that was how we caught him. Upon catching him, he confessed to have stolen my phone but he told us he has dropped it when he was being chased. He added that one Omoga, who was the leader of those that arrested him, was the one who later took the phone from where he dropped it (Onyegbula, Vanguard, Thursday, December 6, 2015).

The perpetrators can also employ distraction to get their victims. As the last account indicates, the victim was focusing on listening to music, and so, it was easier to rob him of his valuable. The major reason Kazeem was robbed of his phone was distraction. In some cases, the use of headset in public places can increase the chances of becoming vulnerable to robbers. But the efforts of people around the area the incident occurred made the robber to be apprehended. So, what is highlighted in this incident is the importance of situational awareness.

There is a higher chance of traffic robbery during heavy traffic. Perpetrators take advantage of slow-moving vehicles to rob drivers and commuters of their properties. According to a police officer at Egbeda:

The criminal syndicate has a mode of operation; they could be five in number spread across one particular area. Two may be stationed in the robbery location while others, in the criminal network would be observing the activities, should there be a problem, the remaining three in the same cycle would beg for the release of others without knowing they are all working together or having same interest. (IDI/Male/Police/Married).

The alarming rate of robbery in traffic has made motorists to express concerns about security in Lagos state. A victim stated that she was still traumatised by a robbery attack

she experienced on a bridge. She narrated that the incident left the two side mirrors of her car broken. The victim narrated:

It happened around 8:00 p.m. I was alone in the car when the armed robbers broke my car windows and demanded my phones and other belongings after attacking the car in front of me. I was speechless and could not utter a word because they looked too dangerous. The robbers, three in number, ransacked my car unhindered; looking for anything they could lay their hands on. The traffic was so serious that nobody could attempt to come to my aid. I could observe that those around were helpless as well, so no need of calling for help. After they were satisfied with ransacking my car, and they didn't find anything valuable on me, they left. We really need police presence on this bridge. (Nwannekanma, Guardian, Thursday, June 24, 2021).

She continued:

When I boarded the bike, the rider was waiting for the second passenger. I should have known earlier when many passengers were trooping out of Ladipo market, and yet, the rider was not calling any of them. Few minutes later, a guy came and the rider called 7/8, Airport junction and the guy immediately jumped on the bike and we moved on. Immediately the rider got under the bridge, he stopped, and the passenger behind grabbed me, gave me a slap and began to ransack me. I thought it was a joke, not until he brought out a very long screwdriver and attempted to pierce my neck. After some struggle, I got overwhelmed because they were two armed guys and they seriously beat the hell out of me after they had injured me on my hand with the screwdriver. They made away with my phone, stripped me of all my belongings, mounted their bike and spirited down the bridge towards Mile two (Nwannekanma and Shedrach, Guardian, Friday, November 26, 2021).

The view in regard to the importance of security presence draws attention to the need for safety and security. And various incidents of traffic robbery have come to the attention of the authorities. But there seems to be no potent strategy to curb them. This shows the need to give attention to efficient law enforcement. Most of the incidents of traffic robbery are spontaneous. Victims usually have no inkling of the operations of the criminals. Most of the incidents happened at nights, when victims are particularly vulnerable. The possibility of the incidents occurring during the day is slim. It has been observed that in areas where there is the presence of the Nigerian police officers, the level of victimisation is reduced.

Another victim of traffic robbery told City Round that she had three run-ins with a specific six-man gang on the bridge, when she reported the alarm on Friday. The victim, a veterinarian, claimed that in one of the incidents, a fierce gang member tore off her gold earring, leaving her bleeding. She recounted her experience:

There are some young robbers who parade as beggars, hawkers and street urchins on Oworonshoki/Gbagada Bridge. They are always there in the traffic. I have been robbed twice at the same spot coming from work and on one occasion, they attacked me and tore my ears in a bid to remove my gold earrings. What happened was that I rolled down slightly to give him money since he asked for money and was hitting my glass aggressively, I thought he was just an aggressive beggar. I tried to roll up the glass back despite my bleeding ears and moved the car immediately the traffic eased a bit. They were trying to force my glass down further and showing their arms and also trying to open my door and asking for my phones (Olasupo, Punch, Saturday, December 10, 2022).

The traffic robbers prey on drivers caught in traffic, exploiting their vulnerability and limited mobility. They lower the guard and instill a false sense of sympathy in their victims by posing as urchins, beggars, or hawkers. They overcome resistance by using physical force and intimidation, such as tearing of clothes and hitting windows.

Another victim relived her revictimisation experience:

It is the same experience on the Maza-Maza-Alakija section of the Lagos-Badagry Expressway every night. There is usually traffic on both sides inward Alakija and

outward Mile 2. These boys with cutlasses usually would demand you drop something for them or get your car vandalised. You are then forced to cooperate when you imagine that what you are parting with is a small fraction of what would be used to repair the car.

(Punch Editorial Board, Saturday, August 6, 2022).

In other cases, perpetrators weaponised the fear of victims as a tool by posing as threats with cutlasses. With this, they induce fear and obedience and pressure victims into succumbing to their whims by taking hard decisions.

A victim of traffic robbery is one who has faced terror, considering the psychological effect the experience can have on the victim. The victim may experience a wide range of negative emotions, including fear, rage, and anxiety. He or she might also struggle to focus, sleep, and build trust with other people. A victim may experience PTSD, or Post-traumatic Stress Disorder, in certain cases.

A victim also shared this experience:

There was traffic gridlock, which hindered vehicles from moving fast. I spent three hours to move from the island to Iyana-Oworo en-route Omole. As I drove past Iyana-Oworo towards Ogudu, a man suddenly appeared from behind, hit my car and ordered me to give him all I had. As I attempted to wind up my car window glass, the guy showed me a butt of a gun that was tucked inside his trousers by his groin. He ordered me to give him my phones. But as I was still fumbling with the phones, he stretched his hands into the car and made away with my bag and two phones (Sunday and Nwannekanma, Guardian, Tuesday, August 25, 2015).

The traffic robbery incident outside Ogudu showed a complex situation marked by helplessness, fear, and even some level of resistance. The robber's sudden appearance and gun threat which accompanied it immediately evoked fear on the victim. The traffic situation caused a sense of entrapment and limited options, making escape challenging. The attempt by victim to wind up the car window signals some form of resilience and an attempt to take control in the midst of a chaotic situation.

Emmanuel Chukwu, a driver, had his cell phone taken away from him at gunpoint on the Kara end of the bridge. Chukwu recounted that the thief approached his car, opened the door, and asked for his valuables by ceasing the opportunity of the traffic. According to him:

I left the office in Magboro around 9pm with a female colleague and as we got to the Kara area, we encountered the gridlock. As we were waiting to get to the front and see what caused the traffic, I saw a young man walking along the divided lane. Unfortunately, I did not lock the door; he opened the door and entered the car and he kept asking for my phone, which I gave him (Punch, Sunday, November 1, 2019).

Another victim equally gave his own account:

They parade the long stretch of the road from Doyin bus stop to the top of the bridge in groups of 10s and 20s and descend heavily on motorists in the traffic build-up. The only people they do not attack are truck drivers, but they always warn them not to intervene whenever they are carrying out their operations, else they will start attacking them also. A vulcanizer operating beside the road said that many commuters and motorists have been shot and wounded; others were also attacked with dangerous weapons along the road, after losing valuable property, including phones, jewelries and many other personal effects (Nnadozie, Onyegbula and Onodjae, 2023).

3. HOTSPOTS OF TRAFFIC ROBBERY IN LAGOS STATE

There are locations in Lagos in which traffic robbery occurs frequently. The hotspots are influenced by temporal factors. Bus stops and train stations may be risky at specific times, particularly at times when there is considerable traffic situation (Brantingham and Brantingham, 1995; Hart and Miethe, 2014). Locations highlighted here, with frequent cases of traffic robbery, may be regarded as crime hotspots (Brantingham and Brantingham, 1984). Public places that show a significant lack of surveillance and security can also be designated as crime hotspots (Ceccato and Oberwittler, 2008; Hart and Miethe, 2014).

4. FELSONIAN AND COHENIAN INTERVENTION: ROUTINE ACTIVITY THEORY

The theoretical approach that can best be used to account for traffic robbery in Lagos, as it relates to drivers and commuters is the Routine Activity theory. Marcus Felson and Cohen Lawrence put forward this theory in 1979. The Routine Activity theory provides a framework that can be used to account for the experiences suffered by victims of traffic robbery. Most criminal acts have made it necessary for considering the likely relationship that exists among offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of capable guardians against crime (Felson and Cohen, 1979). This may be achieved by analysing three factors: motivated offenders, suitable targets, and the absence of guardians.

The implication of this is that before a crime like traffic robbery can take place, an offender must be willing to commit the crime (motivated offenders). In the same vein, before a crime can be perpetuated, there must be a suitable target, which has to do with the presence of a vulnerable victim to receive the effect of the crime. But the absence of a guardian in carrying out a crime implicates the absence of law enforcement agents to prevent a crime from taking place (Turvey and Freeman, 2014). In this way, inanimate objects, like security cameras, can act as capable guardians, because they can give the impression of real-time monitoring, putting perpetrators of crime at a position of being identified and apprehended.

The overlap between victims and offenders of traffic robbery in order to create various opportunities can be explicated by everyday activities of people (Tompson and Bowers, 2015). The presence of law enforcement agents may be limited, which may give offenders more opportunities to victimise commuters in traffic. A proper consideration of this factor is crucial in understanding situations in a high-risk traffic hotspot, given that specific areas, time of the day, and daily routine particularly create vulnerability. Traffic robbers are opportunistic in their operation. Since they are familiar with the terrain and route, it is easier for them to escape. Commuters hit by traffic are particularly vulnerable, because they are not familiar with the route, making them prey to traffic robbers.

The underlying argument in Routine Activity theory is that crime generally occurs, when there is both the opportunity and the ability to commit it. This is dependent on the motivation of the offender, the victim's vulnerability, and the absence of capable guardians (Turvey and Freeman, 2014). The most potent way, perhaps, to avoid traffic robbers is to focus on hardening and avoid unnecessary display of valuables in public either while driving or commuting. Maintaining vigilance and keeping a watchful eye on the door of cars during traffic are also crucial. The Routine Activity theory, therefore, states that every individual is responsible for his or own safety, since everyday activities pose a potential threat to individuals to become victims of criminal activities.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1 Design and study setting

The study was conducted in the Lagos metropolis, such as Ikorodu, Ikeja, Kosofe, Apapa, Agege, Lagos Mainland, Badagry, Mushin, Oshodi-Isolo and Alimosho Local Government Areas in South-West Nigeria. Lagos State was purposively selected, due to the high rate of traffic robbery incidents. The state has also been selected because it is prone to traffic. The study covered all reported cases of traffic robbery incidents in the state. However, it should be acknowledged that some of the incidents were underreported. Traffic robbery in Lagos is a social ill that affects the population and hinders economic development. The vast population of those residents in Lagos move at the same time in order to beat traffic. The presence of bad roads and congestion creates opportunity for traffic robbers and poses security threats. Lagos state is, therefore, a suitable choice for this study.

A cross-sectional design was used in collecting data, and consisted of qualitative and quantitative methods. While the qualitative method was deployed to capture non-numerical data, the quantitative method helped to capture numerical and measurable data. Content analysis was employed to analyse the various experiences of victims in traffic robbery incidents. The Findings from the quantitative and qualitative data were subjected to triangulation in order to aid clearer understanding of traffic robbery. Qualitative data was also used to enrich and contextualise quantitative findings, offering insights into the experiences of victims in traffic robbery.

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News articles and editorials which are related to traffic robbery were collected and analysed from major national dailies, such as Vanguard, Tribune, Punch, The Guardian, and The Sun, from January 2015 to December 2023. The experiences of the victims in traffic robbery were analysed using the method of content analysis. This method was adopted because it can determine specific patterns of words and concepts within texts, and relies on qualitative tools of data collection. To ascertain, for instance, the number of times traffic robbery incidents occur, conceptual analysis was deployed to determine the number of times traffic robbery incidents take place.

The 24 hours in a day were purposively divided into 8 hours, resulting in an interval of three hours, for example: 12AM- 2:59AM, 3AM- 5:59AM, 6AM- 8:59AM to 9PM- 11:59PM. The frequency and percentage of the incidents were also determined. Coded data, patterns and relationship between variables were identified and analysed by using frequency tables and percentages. This is important because the design of the study led to the need to allow participants to be thoroughly engaged and questioned in order to elicit detailed responses in regard to their experiences in traffic robbery. A non-probability sampling technique from news reports was also used due to the nature of the study. Purposive selection of Lagos State was equally done because of the high level of reporting and arresting of criminal suspects involved in traffic robbery.

Primary data sourced from newspaper reports, articles, and editorials were analysed. This is important, given that a broader idea of the nature of experience faced by victims of traffic robbery can be apprehended. The experiences of the victims were collected and analysed by using content analysis. An interview was also conducted with police personnel. Newspaper articles were identified using specific search terms related to traffic robbery incidents in Lagos State, such as "Traffic Robbery." To ensure comprehensive coverage, the month, time, victim demographics, reporter, location of incident, number of suspects involved, robbery dimension, and data were generated using frequency tables and percentages to measure the frequency of the incident. Interviews granted by victims of traffic robbery were also analysed. The daily activities of victims make them vulnerable to traffic robbers. The robbers make use of locations with low security surveillance to attack victims.

5.2 Results

Table 1 findings

To investigate how time significantly influences the occurrence of traffic robbery

With the growing population in Lagos State, with about 16,536,000 people (Macrotrend, n.d), the chances of getting victimised is high, with the rumble and tumble of city life. Timing is important in understanding the experiences of victims of traffic robbery. The vulnerable state of victims to traffic robbery is considered by analysing the relationship between timing and victimization. Timing is a crucial element or significant part of the experience of victims during traffic robbery. Timing is essential for victimisation.

Table 1.0 Does time significantly influence the occurrence of traffic robbery?

Time	Frequency	Percentage
12:00 AM- 2:59AM	4	4.82
3:00 AM- 5:59AM	10	12.05
6:00 AM- 8:59AM	7	8.43
9:00 AM- 11:59AM	4	4.82
12:00 PM- 2:59PM	3	3.61
3:00 PM- 5:59PM	0	0
6:00 PM- 8:59PM	27	32.53
9:00 PM- 11:59PM	28	33.73
	83	100

Source: Field Work 2023

Table 1.0 shows the frequency of times that were reported by various newspapers. The frequency was derived from when most offenders victimised their victims. 33.73% of robberies take place between 9 p.m and 11:59 p.m. This implies that traveling during these hours increases a person's risk of being robbed. Tade and Muhammed (2023) corroborate this, noting that timing is an important part of “one chance” criminality. Many of the cases reported by participants happened late at night, between 9p.m and 11:30 p.m., while very few occurred during the day. Bernasco *et al.* (2016) asserts that a place that presents a good target for robbers late at night, due to an abundance of intoxicated people, might be less attractive during the day when people are rushing to work. In other words, there is high-risk window, especially at night. Additionally, it highlights how crucial it is for police to be proactive in a variety of settings.

The impact of space and time in relation to traffic robbery incidents cannot be overemphasised. Some studies have examined the role of time in traffic robbery incidents. Timing determines whether or not an individual can be a victim of traffic robbers. The proportion of robberies at night during weekdays and during daytime at weekends in metropolitan Lagos has risen sharply, since many more homes are likely to be fully occupied during these periods (Badiora and Ntamark, 2007). Traffic robberies are more likely to occur at night for various reasons. First, robbers take cover from darkness, making it harder for victims to see and recognise them. Second, there is a higher chance of people carrying various valuables or cash late at night. And third, fewer people are out on the streets at night, which can facilitate the ability of robbers to target victims covertly and without detection.

The extent of severity of traffic robberies can also vary, depending on the time of day. A 2007 study, for instance, conducted by the national highway traffic safety administration revealed that nighttime traffic robberies had a higher likelihood of involving violence than daytime traffic robberies. The study also showed that robberies that occur at night are more likely to result in injuries than those that occur during the day (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2007).

Studies have shown that victimisation from traffic robberies is significantly influenced by the time of day. Generally, traffic robberies are more common at night than during the day. In 2003, for instance, a study conducted by the Bureau of Justice Statistics revealed that 63% of traffic robberies took place between 6:00 p.m. and 6:00 a.m. The study also revealed that 10:00 p.m to midnight was the peak hour for traffic robberies (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2003).

A victim shared his experience:

Last night at about 9pm, one guy almost robbed me on 3rd Main Bridge. I was lucky the traffic moved a bit so I moved my car and then he took off (Edeme, Punch, Friday, May 20, 2022).

This interaction takes place between 6pm and 11:59 p.m. This is a high-risk period, when most of traffic robberies occur, as the data showed the robbers took advantage of opportunities. The robbers most likely chose to target the victim, because she was alone in the car, stopped in traffic, and possibly distracted (driving at night). If the traffic had not moved a little, they would have stolen her valuables. This incident enhances our understanding of traffic robberies by emphasising the importance of timing. While the period between 9 p.m. and 11:59 p.m. are considered high-risk, the fact that the incident happened at 10:30 p.m. suggests that the risk may extend slightly beyond that window. Since it is now completely dark, there are fewer police officers on patrol at 10:30 p.m., which presents an opportunity for robbers.

Another respondent from Vanguard said:

If you see what they do to motorists at night, you will cry for this country. They operate as if there are no security agents, or as if they are above the law. Those of us living in Orile or Doyin axis have been victims because, after attacking motorists, they will enter the streets around 12 midnight, share their ill-gotten loot and, when they disagree over sharing pattern and in that state of either drunkenness or influence of drugs, they will start unleashing terror on residents of the areas. We rarely sleep with our two eyes closed every night (Nnadozie, Onyegbula and Onodjae, 2023).

Regular activities like going to work or running errands can lead to predictable movement patterns, which increases a person's vulnerability to being targeted by robbers during these times. (Felson and Clarke, 1993). The timing and location of potential victims and their valuables play a significant role in influencing the decision of robbers. For instance, rush-hour traffic jams can create opportunities for thieves to target cars that are stuck in slow-moving traffic (Block and Block, 2018).

5.3 Discussion of findings

The increase in the rate of migration from rural areas to megacities, like Lagos, may contribute to crime rate. Unemployed youths especially, with no means of living, take to the road to rob victims of their valuables. Traffic robbers study their location before operation. Youth unemployment is, therefore, a major factor in incidents involving traffic robbery. Hindelang, Gottfredson, and Farofalo (1978) argue that certain individuals are more prone to being victims of traffic robbery, due to their behaviours, habits, or customs which increase their exposure to crime. The lifestyle of victims can contribute to their victimization, particularly if their lifestyle involves being in possession of attractive or expensive items. A celebrity, for instance, traveling home from a late-night event may be more vulnerable to traffic robbery, due to their visibility and the presence of valuable items. Thus, everyday activities and lifestyle choices are significant factors that expose individuals to traffic robbery. Robbers often take advantage of situations in which security personnel are either low or absent. With this low level of security presence, the traffic robbers have free rein to carry out their activities, with little or no interruptions, and no chance of being nabbed by law enforcement agents.

6. CONCLUSION

The government of Lagos state should provide a strong security system in areas prone to traffic robbery in order to guarantee a peaceful society. Good lighting system and CCTV should also be installed to cover the activities of criminals in traffic hotspots. In doing this, there is need for the government to set up strategies and map out plans to bring traffic robbers to justice. The security challenge in Lagos can also be addressed from local to state level through security outfits including neighbourhood watch, police, and Man O' War. The Lagos State Government should equally deploy more security personnel to the most frequently reported hotspots of traffic robbery incidents. Commuters should always be vigilant and report cases of traffic-related robbery to the appropriate authority for proper documentation and data collection. This will influence decisions of government in the area of policymaking.

6.1 Recommendation

Victimization occurs when opportunities present themselves to offenders. By so doing, robbers take advantage of situations to victimise their victims. The use of surveillance or lighting up of dark hotspots can reduce the challenge of traffic robbery. More attention should be given to the hours between. 9 p.m and 11:59 p.m, because they constitute threats to drivers and commuters. Conscious efforts should be made to identify more routine activities, so that more preventive strategies can be developed to protect individuals from becoming victims of traffic robbery. There is need for victims to report incidents of traffic robbery, which would aid in shaping policy decisions. In addition, it is

important to deploy police vehicles to areas prone to traffic robbery, especially during rush hour in order to prevent criminals from perpetuating harm against individuals. Residents can also be sensitised on high-risk hours as a way of strengthening prevention strategies.

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